

Dynamic ship lock scheduler for waterway networks

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ABSTRACT:

Uncertain passage times at ship infrastructures, i.e, locks and moveable bridges, are partially due to contemporary operating regimes on European inland waterways. This uncertainty results in added waiting times and fuel consumption. This study presents a dynamic scheduler for a network of ship infrastructures, accommodating so-called mixed traffic of ships with both pre-announced arrivals and ad-hoc announcement at arrival. An iterative approach is presented that a) solves the single infrastructure scheduling problem via best-first tree search, and that b) addresses the interdependency of ship infrastructure passage slots at network level, resulting in a reliable, schedules for the entire waterway network. Comparing the proposed scheduler against a current day regime in simulation shows efficiency improvements. Simulating different scenarios of mixed traffic shows that the proposed scheduler can provide reliable passage slots over multiple scheduling iterations, with efficiency improvement compared to contemporary operating regimes. These results imply that the proposed approach has significant potential in reducing waiting time and fuel consumption compared to current practice.

KEYWORDS: (max. 5 keywords)

Ship lock; scheduling; inland waterway; A* algorithm; simulation

EXTENDED ABSTRACT:

Reduce ship fuel consumption by reliable inland waterway scheduling

Inland Waterborne Transport (IWT) possesses advantages, such as being a low-energy and low CO₂ emitting mode of transportation. However, these advantages are not fully exploited today due to inefficiencies in most ship lock and moveable bridge operations in European inland waterways. Ship navigation on rivers and canals is sub-optimal, leading to vessels that routinely wait unnecessarily at moveable bridges or ship locks. This can be prevented by more accurate and timely scheduling of passages. This requires an innovative operating scheme at ship locks and bridges to provide reliable passage slots in advance, allowing ships to sail at the fuel-optimal speed towards ship locks and bridges (Golak, et al., 2022). In addition, scheduling ship lock moves in advance can be beneficial in optimizing ship lock throughput, resulting in more efficient lock chamber filling and potential to reduce the number of chamber moves in low-water-level periods.

Thus, the main objective of this study is to develop a scheduling system that can manage ship passages at infrastructures (ship locks and moveable bridges) within a waterway network of multiple ship locks and/or moveable bridges, providing the aforementioned benefits compared to current day regime of first-come first-serve.

This study is part of a larger effort in the NOVIMOVE project, which focuses on improvements in inland waterway transport. One of the foreseen improvements is a novel smart river navigation system (SRNS) for inland ship transport, consisting of smart navigation systems (SNSs) and a dynamic scheduling system (DSS). The DSS is responsible for the scheduling of ship lock and bridge passages. The proposed methodology involves ships that use an SNS to optimize their journey by pre-announcing their sailing intentions in the form of a voyage plan, i.e., which infrastructures to pass and the maximal and preferred sailing speeds on the stretches between them. Using these voyage plans, the DSS schedules passage slots for these ships in the inland waterway network. Next to so-called SNS-ships, ships that do not use the SNS are accommodated in the DSS schedule upon arrival at an infrastructure.

The developed DSS approach consists of:

- (1) A methodology to schedule individual infrastructures for a time horizon of several hours.
- (2) A methodology to align schedules of consecutive infrastructures in a waterway.
- (3) An application protocol interface (API) to communicate between the SNSs and the DSS.
- (4) A simulation environment to evaluate the impact of DSS scheduling with current day first-come, first-serve infrastructure operations.

The impact of the developed DSS is evaluated on the Schelde-Rijn waterway network, where three of the busiest ship locks in Europe (Volkerak, Krammer and Kreekrak) connect the seaports of Antwerp and Rotterdam. Due to the higher complexity of lock move scheduling problem compared to a bridge opening scheduling problem, we address here the solution for scheduling a network of ship locks.

Figure 1 A waterway featuring two locks, showing the interdependency in lock scheduling on a waterway..

Dynamic Scheduling System (DSS)

We provide a description of the DSS and its relation with the SNSs before detailing the developed methodologies. In our framework, ships use an SNS to share the ship's voyage plan with the DSS, announcing which infrastructures they intend to pass and both the preferred and minimal travel time for the waterway stretches between these infrastructures. The objectives of the DSS are twofold: first, to assign slots of lock moves such that the travel times between subsequent locks in a voyage are close to the preferred travel time, but not smaller than the minimal travel time on the involved stretch. Second, to ensure reliability, so that slots assigned to the same ship should exhibit limited variation between scheduling and subsequent rescheduling rounds.

In terms of operations, the goal for the DSS is to schedule several hours (e.g., 3 to 6 hours) in advance with real-time information updates and rescheduling every 15 minutes if deemed necessary. The DSS aims to produce quality schedules within 5 minutes of computation time.

Figure 2 Overview of the SNRS (Smart River Navigation System) information flow between ships with SNS (smart navigation system) and the DSS (Dynamic Scheduling System).

Scheduling networks of ship locks

Ji et al. 2022 state that the research on sequential lock scheduling is still rudimentary, with examples in literature investigating specified or simplified problems rather than addressing the so-called Generalized Sequential Lock Scheduling problem (GSLSP). They propose a heuristic algorithmic framework to address the decomposed sequential lock scheduling problem. However, the optimization objectives in their approach do not align directly with the objectives of the smart river navigation system. This study therefore proposes a different decomposition for solving the scheduling problem, which addresses the objectives set for the DSS. A more rudimentary example of foregoing lock scheduling modelling, with single chamber single lock, is presented by (Passchyn, et al., 2016).

Sequential lock scheduling at waterway network level

We first describe the basis of the scheduling process at the waterway network level. The most challenging aspect of this process is that the schedule of a single lock cannot be optimized in isolation, since it depends on that of the neighbouring locks (and vice versa). An iterative search method is hence used to solve the lock interdependency, via the following steps:

1. Scheduling single locks based on estimated ship arrivals at (sequential) locks.

2. Updating arrival times at sequential locks based on the single lock schedules.
3. Verifying the feasibility of all arrival times with respect to sailing speeds and lock move durations; if not feasible, restart the process at step 1, until all assigned lock move slots are feasible.

To execute step 1 of the waterway network scheduling, a method for single lock scheduling is needed. This method is described below.

Single lock scheduling

Scheduling single locks has been decomposed into 3 subproblems:

1. Partition all ships into groups assigned to the same chamber move.
2. Decide how to position these ships in the lock chamber.
3. Determine when to start the chamber move.

Subproblem 3 is formulated as a convex optimization problem. For this we developed an efficient solution method, based on (Lange, 2012), providing the optimal move start time given the minimal and ideal arrival times of all ships in a set of consecutive lock moves. The chamber packing problem (subproblem 2) has been solved using a rule-based heuristic to determine if specific sequences of ships fit in a lock chamber, taking ship sizes and distance requirements (based on cargo t) into account (see, e.g., (Verstichel, et al., 2014)).

The complex nature of deciding which ships to group together (subproblem 1) is resolved using A*, a best-first tree search algorithm. The algorithm builds a tree graph with (partial) solutions, scoring each one via a heuristic. Promising partial solutions are progressively expanded until certain criteria are met, such as reaching a complete solution (i.e., all ships are assigned to a move) while no better (partial) solution is known.

The choice for this exhaustive search approach is driven by its flexibility in implementation, allowing easy adjustment of search parameters and implementation details regarding, e.g., the model used to fit ships inside a chamber. Note that any (partial) solution in the search algorithm is a feasible single lock schedule which allows interrupting the computation at any time. If a complete solution is not yet available, the best partial solution is completed via a greedy method, adding moves for the not yet scheduled ships.

Simulation environments

To test and validate the developed methodologies for scheduling passages at locks, we resorted to two simulation tools. The first tool is an existing validated simulator that implements current practice for lock passages, which we could interface with our DSS via the developed API. The interfacing allows to validate the developed methodologies through benchmarking against current day practices.

Unfortunately, the validated simulator does not allow for adjusting of ship speeds based on the results of our scheduler. I.e., whenever a schedule is produced, a ship cannot adjust its journey to arrive just in time at the lock for its schedule passage. Adjustment of ship speeds is required to get insights into fuel reduction possibilities. Therefore, a second simulation tool was developed, as an alternative to the validated current practices simulation tool. This second simulation capability has lower fidelity but allows for the adjustment of ship speeds.

Validation of the smart navigation system and dynamic scheduling system

The developed methodologies are compared to current practices by using the interface with the validated simulation tool. For this comparison, realistic traffic scenarios for the Schelde-Rijn area have been simulated. First, the simulation tool was used to simulate current practice as a benchmark. Secondly, these benchmark schedules are compared to those produced with our developed methodologies inside the same simulation tool. Note that the simulated scenario assumes no ships have an SNS. Thus, DSS does not obtain ship voyage plans in advance. Rather, ships announce their arrival in proximity to a lock, in line with current practice. The result of this comparison is given in Figure 3. Even with no pre-announced arrival information, DSS achieves a significant reduction in waiting time per ship, which on average drops from 23 to 14 minutes.

Figure 3: Average waiting time in the simulator without and with using DSS and 0% SNS-ships.

The second simulation capability was used to investigate the potential for reduction in waiting time and fuel consumption when ships adopt SNS, thus adjusting their sailing speed based on schedules produced by the DSS. Three scenarios were evaluated: 0%, 50% and 100% adoption of SNS. The same locks and traffic intensity inputs were used as in the previous comparison. The results for the three scenarios are depicted in Figure 4. As expected, when 100% of the ships adopt SNS, a waiting time of almost 0 at the locks can be achieved, due to all ships adjusting their sailing speed. Note that there is a difference between the waiting times for 0% SNS in this second simulation capability compared with the waiting time in the capability of simulation in the current practice simulation. This difference is assumed to be caused by both a difference in simulation fidelity as well as a difference in waiting time calculation. In particular, in the current practice simulation, ships waiting for other ships to enter or vacate a chamber are considered waiting, while they are not in the second simulation capability.

Figure 4: Average waiting time in the DSS simulator with different shares of SNS in the ship fleet.

Reducing the waiting time by adjusting the sailing speed is one of the goals of the SRNS. The most relevant impact of the DSS results lies in the possible fuel consumption reduction SNS-ships could realize by reducing sailing speed to arrive just-in-time before the lock moves. For some ships sailing speeds can be reduced up to 10%, with potential fuel savings up to 20% (CESNI, 2020). This shows the important role of the DSS in enabling efficient navigation for SNS-ships.

Another objective of the DSS is to ensure reliable passage times for ships over subsequent (re)scheduling rounds. This reliability is quantified by monitoring passage times per ship for each lock over scheduling iterations. Typically, a ship, especially one equipped with SNS, is allocated to a slot across multiple scheduling rounds, given the relatively short intervals between successive scheduling rounds. In cases where multiple slot times are allocated to a

ship, we compute the standard deviation for the set of slot times per ship per lock as an indication of the reliability of the schedules from the perspective of the ship.

The results of this computation (Table 1) indicate that the vast majority of slot assignments exhibit a standard deviation less than 15 minutes, indicating that the DSS produces reliable schedules. Also, comparing the 0% with the 100% SNS case indicates a reduction in both mean standard deviation and number of cases in which standard deviation exceeds 15 minutes, suggesting that widespread adoption of SNS would improve overall reliability. However, the case of 50% SNS has a higher number of standard deviations exceeding 15 minutes. This increase is attributed to the algorithm's dual objective: it aims to be reliable for previously assigned ships in slots, while it also has to accommodate arriving non-SNS-ships to the schedule.

Table 1: Statistics of reliability for lock passage slot times per ship for subsequent scheduling rounds based on standard deviation of recurring, rescheduled, assigned lock move times for a ship at an infrastructure.

	0% SNS	50% SNS	100% SNS
<u>Number of simulated lock passage slots occurring in subsequent scheduling rounds.</u>	<u>2327</u>	<u>3394</u>	<u>4424</u>
Mean of ship lock passage standard deviations - minutes	1.7	2.9	1.55
Median of ship lock passage standard deviations - minutes	0	0.93	0
Maximum of ship lock passage standard deviations - minutes	25.17	38.94	89.83
Minimum of ship lock passage standard deviations - minutes	0	0	0
Number of standard deviations over 15 minutes. (%)	<u>42 (2%)</u>	<u>91 (3%)</u>	<u>66 (1%)</u>

The computational time required for these experiments is below 5 minutes per scheduling round. However, the scalability of the presented solution is currently constrained, as computational requirements grow exponentially with an increase in the number of ships and locks. Our implementation of the proposed method allows for scheduling up to 80 ships each up to 3 hours in advance. These schedules are made for a waterway network with 3 ship locks and 3 chambers per ship lock, within a 5-minute timeframe. on a single core of an Intel i7 1.90 GHz notebook. Possible avenues for improvements in computational time include speeding up the A* search with fine-tuned heuristics; exploiting parallelism in the scheduling of multiple infrastructures at the same time; reducing the number of iterations required to achieve a feasible schedule on the network of waterways.

Reliable lock moves and fuel consumption reduction for future logistic systems

The developed Dynamic Ship lock Scheduler (DSS) provides a methodology to schedule networks of waterway for several hours in advance for a barging system with pre-announcing and ad-hoc announcing ship arrivals. It includes packing of lock chambers given ship sizes and takes into account rules on not combining cargo with higher risk goods or professional and recreational traffic.

Experiments with the developed DSS demonstrate a reduction in waiting times, which indicates increased ship lock throughput. Waiting times are further reduced the more ships adopt the SNS and adjust their speeds according to given slots, which can result in fuel savings.

In addition, our second experiment indicates that the resulting schedules are sufficiently reliable. We highlight that mixed SNS and non-SNS traffic is a scenario of interest and of added complexity for future research. This also supports the rationale that the effectiveness of a lock scheduling system depends on the share of ships that participate in the system.

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